

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On Some Geometrical Properties of Proximal Sets and Existence of Best Proximity Points

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ABSTRACT

The notion of proximal intersection property and diagonal property is introduced and used to establish some existence of the best proximity point for mappings satisfying contractive conditions.

Key words: Best proximity point, proximal sets, UC property, proximal intersection property, diagonal property

Mathematics Subject Classifications: MSC 2010, 47H09

INTRODUCTION

Let X be a non-empty set and f be a self-map of X . An element $x \in X$ is called a fixed point of f if $f(x) = x$. Fixed point theorems deal with sufficient conditions on X and f which ensure the existence of fixed points. Suppose the fixed point equation $f(x) = x$ does not possess a solution, then the natural interest is to find an element $x \in X$, such that x is in proximity to $f(x)$ in some sense. In other words, we would like to get a desirable estimate for the quantity $d(x, f(x))$.

It is natural that some mapping, especially non-self mappings defined on a metric space (X, d) , do not necessarily possess a fixed point that is $d(x, f(x)) > 0$ for all $x \in X$. In such situations, it is reasonable to search for existence and uniqueness of the point $x \in X$ such that $d(x, f(x)) = 0$. In other words, one speculates to determine an approximate solution x that is optimal in the sense that the distance between x and $f(x)$ is minimum. Here, the point x is the best proximity point. That is $d(x, f(x)) = d(A, B)$ Where $d(A, B) = \inf \{d(x, y) : x \in A, y \in B\}$.

Best proximity results is also interesting for the geometrical properties of the underlying space. In Suzuki *et al.*,^[1] UC property was introduced to prove some existence results on best proximity point. In Raj and Eldred,^[2] the author introduced p-property and proved strict convexity is equivalent to p-property.

We introduce proximal intersection property and diagonal property for a pair (A, B) where A and B are nonempty closed subsets of metric space. We show that every pair (A, B) of a real Hilbert space satisfies diagonal property. Then, these properties are used to establish the existence of best proximity point for mapping satisfying some contractive conditions introduced by Wong.^[3]

PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we give some basic definitions and concepts that are related to the context of our main results.

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Definition 2.1^[4]

Let A and B be nonempty subsets of a metric space (X, d) . Then, (A, B) is said to satisfy property UC if the following holds: If x_n and x'_n are sequences in A and y_n is a sequence in B such that $\lim_n d(x_n, y_n) = d(A, B)$ and $\lim_n d(x'_n, y_n) = d(A, B)$, then $\lim_n d(x_n, x'_n) = 0$ holds.

Definition 2.2

Let A and B be nonempty subsets of a metric space (X, d) . Then, (A, B) is said to satisfy proximal intersection property if whenever $A_n \subset A$ and $B_n \subset B$ are a decreasing sequence of closed subsets such that $\delta(A_n, B_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$. Then $\bigcap A_n = \{x\}, \bigcap B_n = \{y\}$ with $d(x, y) = d(A, B)$.

Remark 2.1

$d(A, B) = d(\bar{A}, \bar{B})$ and $\delta(A, B) = \delta(\bar{A}, \bar{B})$ where $\delta(A, B) = \sup\{\|x - y\| : x \in A, y \in B\}$.

Definition 2.3^[2]

Let X be a metric space and let $f : X \rightarrow X$. Then, d_f is the function on $X \times X$ defined by

$$d_f(x, y) = \inf\{d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) : n \geq 1\}, x, y \in X \tag{1}$$

Definition 2.4^[3]

Let A and B be nonempty subsets of a metric space X . We shall use X_d to denote the set

$$\{r' : \text{for any } s > r', d(x, y) - d(A, B) \in [r', s] \text{ for some } x \in A, y \in B\} \tag{2}$$

Remark 2.2

If $r' \in X_d$, then, there exists $x_n \in A, y_n \in B$ such that $d(x_n, y_n) - d(A, B) \rightarrow r'$. Also if $x \in A, y \in B$, then $d(x, y) - d(A, B) \in X_d$ and if $x_n \in A, y_n \in B$ such that $d(x_n, y_n) - d(A, B) \rightarrow r'$ then $r' \in X_d$.

Definition 2.5

Let (A, B) be proximal pair of a metric space X . Then, (A, B) is said to satisfy diagonal property if whenever $s_n, t_n \in A$ and $s'_n, t'_n \in B$ are bounded sequences such that $d(s_n, s'_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$ and $d(t_n, t'_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$ then $d(s_n, t'_n) - d(s'_n, t_n) \rightarrow 0$.

Lemma 2.1^[1]

Let A and B be nonempty subsets of a metric space (X, d) . Then, (A, B) has the property UC. Let $\{x_n\}$ and $\{y_n\}$ be sequences in A and B , respectively, such that either of the following holds:

$$\limsup_{m \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{n \geq m} d(x_m, y_n) = d(A, B) \text{ or}$$

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{m \geq n} d(x_m, y_n) = d(A, B)$$

Then $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy.

MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 3.1

Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a complete metric space X satisfying UC property. Let A_n, B_n be decreasing sequence of nonempty closed subsets of X such that $\delta(A_n, B_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then, $\bigcap A_n = \{x\}, \bigcap B_n = \{y\}$ with $d(x, y) = d(A, B)$ that is (A, B) satisfies proximal intersection property.

Proof

Construct a sequence x_n, y_n in X by selecting $x_n \in A_n, y_n \in B_n$ for each $n \in N$.

Since $A_{n+1} \subseteq A_n, B_{n+1} \subseteq B_n$ for all n , we have $x_n \in A_n \subseteq A_m, y_n \in B_n \subseteq B_m$ for all $n > m$.

We claim that x_n is a Cauchy sequence.

Let $\epsilon > 0$ be given.

Since $\delta(A_n, B_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$, there exists a positive integer N such that $\delta(A_n, B_n) < d(A, B) + \epsilon$, for all

$n \geq N$.

Since A_n, B_n are decreasing sequences, we have $A_n, A_m \subseteq A_N$ and $B_n, B_m \subseteq B_N$ for all $m, n \geq N$. Therefore, $x_n, x_m \in A_N$ and $y_n, y_m \in B_N$ for all $m, n \geq N$, and thus we have

$$d(x_n, x_m) \leq \delta(A_n, B_n) < d(A, B) + \epsilon \text{ for all } m, n \geq N \tag{3}$$

Since A and B satisfy UC property from lemma 2.1 x_n is a Cauchy sequence. There exists $x \in A$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x$. Similarly, there exists $y \in B$ such that $y_n \rightarrow y$.

We claim that $x \in \cap A_n, y \in \cap B_n$.

Since A_n and B_n are closed for each n , $x \in A_n, y \in B_n$ for all $n \in N$.

Since $d(x_n, y_n) \rightarrow d(A, B)$ we have $d(x, y) = d(A, B)$.

Finally to establish that x is the only point in $\cap A_n$,

If $x_1 \neq x_2 \in \cap A_n$, then $d(x_1, x_2) = d(A, B)$

UC property forces $x_1 = x_2$. Similarly $\cap B_n = \{y\}$.

Lemma 3.1

Let A and B be nonempty closed convex subsets of a real Hilbert space. For every bounded sequence $u_n, v_n \in A$ and $u'_n, v'_n \in B$, we have if $\|u_n - v_n\|$ and $\|u'_n - v'_n\| \rightarrow d(A, B)$ then

- 1) $(u_n - v_n) - (u'_n - v'_n) \rightarrow 0$.
- 2) $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\|u_n - v_n\| - \|v_n - u'_n\|) = 0$.

Proof

Let u_n, v_n be sequences in A and u'_n, v'_n be sequences in B such that

$$\|u_n - u'_n\| \rightarrow d(A, B) \text{ and } \|v_n - v'_n\| \rightarrow d(A, B) \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Let } \epsilon_n = \langle v'_n - u'_n, u'_n - u_n \rangle \tag{5}$$

Since B is convex, $\lambda v'_n + (1 - \lambda)u'_n \in B$ for all $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$

$$\|u_n - v'_n\|^2 = \|u_n - u'_n\|^2 + \|u'_n - v'_n\|^2 + 2\langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle \tag{6}$$

$$\|v_n - u'_n\|^2 = \|v_n - v'_n\|^2 + \|v'_n - u'_n\|^2 + 2\langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle \tag{7}$$

$$\text{Using the identity } \frac{1}{4} (\|x + y\|^2 - \|x - y\|^2) = \langle x, y \rangle \tag{8}$$

Since $\|u_n - (\lambda v'_n + (1 - \lambda)u'_n)\| \geq d(A, B)$ for all n , $\limsup (\lambda \|u'_n - v'_n\|^2 + 2\epsilon_n) \geq 0$.

Letting $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ $\limsup \epsilon_n \geq 0$. Similarly, $\liminf \epsilon_n \geq 0$.

$$\text{Therefore, } \limsup \langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle \geq 0 \tag{9}$$

$$\liminf \langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle \geq 0 \tag{10}$$

Let $s_n = u_n - u'_n$ and $s'_n = v_n - v'_n$.

Suppose $s_n - s'_n \rightarrow 0$ there exists a subsequence n_k such that $\|s_{n_k} - s'_{n_k}\| \geq \epsilon_0$ for some ϵ_0 .

For this, $\epsilon > 0$ there exists N such that for all $n_k \geq N$,

$$\|u_{n_k} - u'_{n_k}\| \leq d(A, B) + \epsilon \tag{11}$$

$$\|v_{n_k} - v'_{n_k}\| \leq d(A, B) + \epsilon \tag{12}$$

From the parallelogram law, for all $n_k \geq N$,

$$\left\| \frac{(u_{n_k} - u'_{n_k}) + (v_{n_k} - v'_{n_k})}{2} \right\|^2 \leq \left\| \frac{(d(A, B) + \epsilon)}{2} \right\|^2 + \left\| \frac{(d(A, B) + \epsilon)}{2} \right\|^2 - \left(\frac{\epsilon_0}{2} \right)^2 \tag{13}$$

As there exists $\epsilon > 0$ such that the R.H.S. is strictly less than $(d(A, B))^2$ a contradiction.

Therefore $\Rightarrow s_n - s'_n \rightarrow 0$

Let $\limsup \langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle = \limsup (\langle s_n - s'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle + \langle v_n - v'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle) \geq 0$

As u_n and v_n are bounded sequences $\limsup \langle v_n - v'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle \geq 0$ (14)

But $\limsup \langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle \geq 0$ analogous to (9) (15)

$\limsup -\langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle \geq 0$ from (14) (16)

$\Rightarrow -\liminf \langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle \geq 0$ (17)

Also $\liminf \langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle \geq 0$ is also true being analogous to (10)

$\Rightarrow \liminf \langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle = 0$ (18)

Replacing \liminf and \limsup in the above arguments we have

$\limsup \langle v_n - v'_n, v'_n - u'_n \rangle = 0$ (19)

Similarly

$\liminf \langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle = 0$ (20)

$\limsup \langle u_n - u'_n, u'_n - v'_n \rangle = 0$ (21)

From 18,19 and 20,21 and from 6,7

We get the desired result, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\|u_n - v'_n\| - \|v_n - u'_n\|) = 0$.

Lemma 3.2

Let A and B be non empty closed subsets of a complete metric space X such that (A, B) satisfying UC property. Let $f : A \cup B \rightarrow A \cup B$ be continuous. Suppose that $f(A) \subset B, f(B) \subset A$ be a continuous function such that

(a) $\inf \{d(x, f(x)) : x \in A\} = d(A, B) = \inf \{d(x, f(x)) : x \in A\} = d(A, B)$

(b) There exists $\delta_n > 0$ such that $d(f(x), f(y)) - d(A, B) < \frac{1}{n}$ whenever $\max \{d(x, f(x)) - d(A, B), d(y, f(y)) - d(A, B)\} < \delta_n$ and $x \in A', y \in B'$ where A' and B' are any closed bounded sets of A and B , respectively.

Then, there exists a best proximity point $x \in A$ such that $d(x, f(x)) = d(A, B)$. Further, if $d(f(x), f(y)) = d(x, y)$ for all $x \in A, y \in B$ then the best proximity point is unique.

Proof

Let $A_n = \left\{ x \in A : d(x, f(x)) - d(A, B) \leq \frac{1}{n} \right\}$

$B_n = \left\{ y \in B : d(y, f(y)) - d(A, B) \leq \frac{1}{n} \right\}$

Since f is continuous, A_n and B_n are closed.

From (a) A_n and B_n are nonempty, there exists N for all $n \in N$.

Let $x \in A_n, y \in B_n$ then $d(x, f(x)) - d(A, B) < \delta_n$ and $d(y, f(y)) - d(A, B) < \delta_n$.

From (b) $d(f(x), f(y)) - d(A, B) \leq \frac{1}{n}$ where $\delta_n \rightarrow 0$.

For any $x \in A_n, y \in B_n, d(f(x), f(y)) - d(A, B) \leq \frac{1}{n}$

Which implies $\delta(f(A_n), f(B_n)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$

and hence $\delta(\overline{f(A_n)}, \overline{f(B_n)}) \rightarrow d(A, B)$.

By proximal intersection criterion for completeness

We have $\bigcap_{n \geq 1} \overline{f(A_n)} = y$, and $\bigcap_{n \geq 1} \overline{f(B_n)} = x$ and $d(x, y) = d(A, B)$.

Thus for each $n \geq 1$, there exists $x_n \in A_n$ such that $d(y, f(x_n)) < \frac{1}{n}$

Since $d(x_n, f(x_n)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$, and $d(y_n, f(y_n)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$.

By UC property $x_n \rightarrow x$.

Since A_n is closed, $x \in A_n$ for each n . This implies $d(x, f(x)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$.

Similarly, $y_n \rightarrow y$ such that $d(y, f(y)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$.

To prove uniqueness,

$d(x, f(x)) = d(A, B)$ and $d(x', f(x')) = d(A, B)$

Since f is non-expansive $d(f^2(x'), f(x')) = d(A, B)$

which implies $f^2(x') = x'$

As $d(x, f(x)) = d(f(x'), f^2(x')) = d(A, B)$.

From (b) $d(f(x), x') = d(f(x), f^2(x')) = d(A, B)$ which implies $x = x'$.

Theorem 3.2

Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a metric space X and let $f : A \cup B \rightarrow A \cup B$ be continuous such that $f(A) \subset B, f(B) \subset A$. Suppose that there exists $\phi : X_d \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ such that $d(x, y) - d(A, B) \leq \phi((x, y) - d(A, B))$ for all $x \in A, y \in B$ and $\sup_{s > r} \inf_{t \in [r, s]} (t - \phi(t)) > 0$ for $r \in X_d - \{0\}$. Then, $d_f(x, y) = d(A, B)$ for all $x \in A, y \in B$. Hence, $\inf \{d(x, f(x)) : x \in A\} = d(A, B)$.

Proof

Suppose to the contrary that there exists $x \in A, y \in B$ such that

$$\inf \{d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) : n \geq 1\} > d(A, B) \tag{22}$$

By hypothesis, there exists $s \in (r', \infty)$ such that

$$u = \inf_{t \in [r', s]} (t - \phi(t)) > 0 \text{ where } r' = r - d(A, B).$$

Since there exists a sequence $d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \rightarrow r'$, where $r' \in X_d - \{0\}$.

Let $t \in (0, s - r')$, i.e. $t < s - r' \Rightarrow r' + t < s$.

Then, from (5), we have

$$d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \rightarrow r' + t < s \text{ for some } n \geq 1.$$

Since $d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \in [r', s]$

$$u \leq d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) - \phi(d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B))$$

$$\phi(d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B)) \leq d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) - u \tag{23}$$

If $f^n(x) \in A, f^n(y) \in B$ and vice versa.

It follows that

$$d_f(x, y) - d(A, B) \leq d_f(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \tag{24}$$

$$\leq d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \tag{25}$$

$$\leq \phi(d(f^n(x), f^n(y))) - d(A, B) \tag{26}$$

$$\leq d(f^n(x), f^n(y)) - d(A, B) \text{ from (23)} \tag{27}$$

$$< r' + t - u \tag{28}$$

Letting $t \rightarrow 0$, we have

$$d_f(x, y) - d(A, B) \leq r' - u \tag{30}$$

$$d_f(x, y) - d(A, B) \leq r - d(A, B) - u \tag{31}$$

$$d_f(x, y) \leq r - u \tag{32}$$

a contradiction.

Theorem 3.3

Let A and B be nonempty closed subsets of a metric space X . Suppose (A, B) satisfies UC property and diagonal property. Let f be as in theorem 3.2, then f satisfies all the conditions of Lemma 3.2 and therefore f has a unique best proximity point.

Proof

Clearly, from theorem 3.2, (a) of lemma 3.2 satisfied.

To prove (b) of lemma 3.2 assume $x_n \in A$ and $y_n \in B$ are bounded sequences

Then, $d(x_n, f(x_n))$ and $d(y_n, f(y_n)) \rightarrow d(A, B)$ where x_n and y_n are sequences of A and B , respectively.

Suppose $d(x_n, f(x_n)) - d(A, B) \rightarrow 0$

Since x_n, y_n are bounded sequence, there exists subsequence n_k and $r > 0$ such that

$$d(f(x_{n_k}), f(y_{n_k})) - d(A, B) \rightarrow r > 0$$

Clearly, $r \in X_d$.

$$\text{Let } r_{n_k} = d(f(x_{n_k}), f(y_{n_k})) - d(A, B) \text{ and } s_{n_k} = d(x_{n_k}, y_{n_k}) - d(A, B)$$

Given $r_{n_k} - s_{n_k} \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ from diagonal property.

$$d(f(x_{n_k}), f(y_{n_k})) - d(A, B) \leq d(f(x_{n_k}), f(y_{n_k})) - d(A, B)$$

Therefore,

$$r_{n_k} \leq \phi(s_{n_k}) \tag{33}$$

Now from 33

$$0 > \phi(s_{n_k}) - s_{n_k}$$

$$= \phi(s_{n_k}) - r_{n_k} + r_{n_k} - s_{n_k}$$

$$\geq r_{n_k} - s_{n_k}$$

Since $r_{n_k} - s_{n_k} \rightarrow 0$ we have $\liminf (\phi(s_{n_k}) - s_{n_k}) = 0$.

Contradicting $\inf_{t \in [r_0, s]} (t - \phi(t)) > 0$ where $s_{n_k} \downarrow r_0$.

This completes the proof.

REFERENCES

1. Suzuki T, Kikkawa M, Vetro C. The existence of best proximity points in metric spaces with the property UC. *Nonlinear Anal* 2009;71:2918-26.
2. Raj VS, Eldred AA. A characterization of strictly convex spaces and applications. *J Optim Theory Appl* 2014;160:703-10.
3. Wong CS. Fixed point theorems for nonexpansive mappings. *J Math Anal Appl* 1972;37:142-50.
4. Eldred AA. Ph.D Thesis. Madras: Indian Institutes of Technology; 2007.